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Research Article

**AWARENESS OF TYPE ONE DIABETES PRESENTING
SYMPTOMS AMONG CAREGIVERS OF UNAFFECTED
CHILDREN IN SAUDI ARABIA****Dr. Mesaed AlSenani, Dr. Shaden alsugheir, Dr. Syed Jamil, Dr. Abdulaziz AlKhalidi,
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Article Received: November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract**

Type 1 diabetes is a common endocrine disorder among children. The yearly diagnosed cases can reach up to 65,000 children worldwide (1). The onset of symptoms of DM1 usually develops at childhood and adolescence, although it can occur later in life(2). In Saudi Arabia, studies reported an increase in the incidence and prevalence rates of DM1 among children and adolescents(3,4). The signs and symptoms of diabetes type one (DM1) at the initial presentation in children can range from mild symptoms such as polyuria, polydipsia, weight loss, lethargy to a moderate/severe (life-threatening) complication as Diabetic Ketoacidosis (DKA) (5.) DKA is a life-threatening serious complication of DM1 with high morbidity and mortality rates (5). According to a study conducted in the western region of Saudi Arabia, acute complications of diabetic ketoacidosis occur in 65.4% of patients (6). Early recognition of symptoms and prompt management can prevent DKA. DKA as the first presentation of type 1 DM varies between countries, the highest frequencies are reported in the United Arab of Emirates (80%) and Saudi Arabia (59%) (5). While in Canada and Sweden it was only 18 and 14 percent respectively (1,5) The difference in the incidence of DKA at first presentation of type 1 DM between different countries was contributed to various factors among which public awareness was considered to be a key factor (5).

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INTRODUCTION:

Increased awareness level of the general population about initial signs and symptoms of DM1 enables early detection and reduce the likelihood of developing DKA (7). This was supported by many studies looking at the awareness level as a protective factor in reducing the rate of life-threatening DKA at first presentation. For instance, in a UK study, parental awareness of early signs and symptoms of DM1 was found to be a protective factor from presentation in DKA (4). In another study that was carried in Finland, children with at least one parent who is educated and had an academic degree had a lower incidence of DKA at presentation (5). Awareness campaigns launched in Australia and France had a great impact on the prevention of DKA (8,9).

There is a lack in the literature regarding the level of awareness of type 1 DM presentation in children among the caregivers in Saudi Arabia. Therefore, in our study, we aimed to assess the awareness level of Saudi caregivers regarding the disease and its presentation, along with their knowledge of the best course of action to take once Diabetes is suspected in a child. This determined areas of knowledge and deficit, which helped to assess the need for educational effort and awareness campaigns.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was conducted from January 2019 to June 2019 in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. A cross-sectional study was carried out using a pre-designed questionnaire. It was distributed to Saudi parents of non-diabetic children visiting outpatient clinics at our tertiary children hospital in Riyadh. A questionnaire translated into Arabic was administered by co-authors to Saudi Parents of unaffected children. Informed consent was obtained and instructions of the survey were explained to the participants. The survey included 377 parents who were randomly selected and interviewed. The data was gathered by a questionnaire obtained from a similar study which was done in Cambridge, UK (10). The questionnaire was divided into 4 sections which included: Section (A) for caregiver demographic data. Section (B) assesses caregiver's awareness of diabetes type one. Section (c) knowledge about the best next step to follow once diabetes is suspected in a child. Section (D) awareness of diabetic ketoacidosis. An educational leaflet from the Saudi ministry of health was distributed after the completion of the questionnaire to the parents. We believe the finding of our study helped to decide the need for such content in the future.

Statistical Analysis:

In this study, statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software. Results were expressed as

odds ratios with 95% confidence interval. P-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant. Performance on the knowledge-based survey was assessed according to the number of correct answers. The demographic data of the entire group was evaluated by calculating means and standard deviations for continuous variables and proportions for categorical values

RESULTS:

In our study, 377 participants have responded to our survey. 211 were females (56%) and 166(44%) were males. We targeted the primary care providers mainly parents of children and the age mean was 38.8 with 10.3 standard deviations. Among these parents, 50% had 4 children or more, 13% had only one child, 20% four children, 18% three children, 17% two children. The educational level was 224(59%) bachelor's degree, 12(3%) no educational background, 19(5%) higher education. 245(65%) of the participants have a relative with diabetes. The majority of 212(86%) were relative with type 2 diabetes. Additionally, we asked about the relationship with the diabetic patient, 171(70%) were first-degree relative and 74(30%) second-degree relative. Moreover, we asked the participant whether they have received awareness about diabetes or not. 233(62%) reported yes they have and doctors and internet commonest method. we asked, "do you have a healthcare provider in your family (like a nurse, dentist, doctor)?" and 249(66%) had a health care practitioner in their families.

The main question in our study was about recognizing the commonest signs and symptoms of diabetes which are frequent urination, thirst, low weight, and fatigue. From the 377, 233(62%) have recognized the disease. Furthermore, we asked the most appropriate next step to take once diabetes is suspected in a child, only 180(47%) have chosen the correct step, which was taking the child to a clinic or ER urgently. We have looked into different variables that may affect the ability to recognize the disease and taking the appropriate first step. For recognizing the disease, knowing someone with diabetes has significantly affected their outcome (p-value= <.0001) (Table1.0). However, the relation with the person (first relative vs other) has no significant on the outcome, type of diabetes as well. Additionally, the participants who received awareness about diabetes had a statistically significant influence on their outcome (p-value= <.0001). On the other hand, the method of awareness was not significant. Lastly, the presence of a health care provider in the family influenced the ability to recognize the signs and symptoms of diabetes (p-value= <.0001). The other demographic variables were not significant. In addition to this, we have also looked at the variables and their effect on selecting the appropriate next step. 70% of the females'

participants have chosen the correct next step whereas male participants only 30%. (p-value=<.0001) (Table 2.0). Similarly, the monthly income for the family influenced their choice, and families with lower income thought that visiting the ER or clinic urgently was the correct next step (p-value=<.0149). Moreover, the number of children in the family also was significant (p-value=0.0408), and families with more children choose the correct step (Figure 3.0). Also, families with the first relative with diabetes have better knowledge about the correct step (p-value =0.0101). Differently from recognizing the disease, the method of awareness influenced taking the correct step (p-value=0.0046).

DISCUSSION:

Our study included 377 participants, 233(62%) of them have recognized the disease. We believe that a high awareness level about diabetes is due to the high incidence of diabetes mellitus in Saudi Arabia. Currently, Saudi Arabia ranks the second-highest in the Middle East and is seventh in the world for the rate of diabetes mellitus type 2. The participants who have had a family member with DM recognized the common signs and symptoms of DM which is thirst, fatigue, frequent urination weight change more than the participants who did not have a diabetic person in their family (p-value <.0001). Moreover, the relation with that family member did not affect the ability to recognize DM (p-value=0.6934). Therefore, if a person had a first relative or any other type of relative or friend with diabetes that person is more likely to recognize the symptoms (p-value=0.9153). Also, the person who received awareness about diabetes is more likely to recognize the disease (p-value=<.0001), regardless of the method of awareness whether it is from a doctor, campaign, information leaflet, internet or other ways (p-value=0.7680). Additionally, having healthcare practitioners in the family had a significant influence on the participants' ability to recognize the disease (p-value=<.0001). Other demographics, however, such as age, gender, monthly income, number of children, and educational level were not significant. Ori Eyal et al reported that parental educational level and socioeconomic status have a protective effect on the presentation DKA(11).

The ability to recognize the signs and symptoms of diabetes mellitus alone is not enough. Parents should take an active action to diagnose and manage T1DM to prevent the complication such as DKA. Additionally, it is important to realize that the highest frequencies for DKA at the presentation of T1DM are reported in Saudi Arabia (44.9%) in compare to Canada (18.6%), and Sweden (14%). With this in mind, we asked the participants about the appropriate action to take if they suspect diabetes in their children. After that, we suggested multiple options to the parents, and we considered that "going

to the clinic urgently or visiting the ER" is the correct step. On the other hand, the other suggested options we considered to be an incorrect step. The other options were:

1. I am going to start my child on a diet and exercise and monitor symptoms.
2. I will consult a relative or friend with diabetes.
3. I will monitor my child's blood sugar from home or the nearest pharmacy.
4. I will see a doctor when I get free time.

Only 180(47%) of the participants choose the correct step in compare to 233(62%) that have recognized the disease signs and symptoms. We studied the variables that affected the parent to choose the correct step, and we found that they are different from the demographics that affected the recognition of disease. For instance, gender was significantly affecting the participants to take the correct step; Mothers and female caregivers were more likely to choose the correct step than fathers or male caregivers. Additionally, the monthly income of the family was significant too, the lower the income the more likely to choose the correct step (p-value=0.0149). Similarly, the number of children has a significant impact on the parent choice of the next step, the more children the parent has the more likely to choose the correct step (p-value=0.0408). Differently from recognizing the disease, knowing a person with diabetes did not influence the choice of the correct step (p-value=0.5133). However, the relation with the person did affect the choice, and the participant who knows a first relative with diabetes was more likely to choose the correct step (p-value=0.0101). Likewise, the method of awareness did affect the choice of the correct step, differently from recognizing disease (p-value=0.0046). There has been a systematic review which included nineteen articles about public knowledge and awareness of diabetes mellitus (DM) among the population of Saudi Arabia. In this study, they included the following population: DM patients (n=13), healthcare workers (n=3), medical students (n=1), secondary school students (n=1), and general population (n=1). Most studies found a lack of public awareness of the risk factors and complications of DM. However, in our study, we had a specific population "primary caregivers" and studying only presenting symptoms of diabetes mellitus type one (12). In a different study done on parents of diabetic children showed poor knowledge about T1DM. One of the major knowledge deficiencies was blood glucose levels in DKA with only 10.8% answered correctly form 120 parents. However, because these parents have diabetic children, we assume that they received more education about diabetes, but still lacking good knowledge. Unlike our findings, this study showed a significant correlation between parent's knowledge

and educational level (13). In another study done in the USA on 276 patients with T1DM, 29% of which had DKA in the presentation. Initially, the commonest symptoms of presentation were:

1. polyuria and polydipsia 94%
2. weight loss 69%
3. Abdominal pain 35%
4. Lethargy 28%
5. Kussmaul breathing 25%

In this study, 77 patients had a delay in diagnosis i.e. diagnosed after the second/later visits. Additionally, they found having a family history of T1DM reduced late presentation with DKA. Similar to our study results which we found a statistically significant correlation between choosing a good course of action and parents with the first relative with diabetes (14). After all, it is important to recognize the initial symptoms of T1DM not only to avoid DKA but also there has been a study which showed poor long-term glycemic control in a patient who initially presented with DKA. Independent, from other demographics and socioeconomic status of the patient (15). After the interview with the participants, we offered an information leaflet from the Saudi Ministry of Health (MOH) to increase

awareness. However, after seeing the results of our study we reviewed the leaflet and it did not include the recommendation to seek urgent medical assessment. Also, we reviewed the videos for the diabetes campaigns done by Saudi MOH, and most of the videos focused on diabetes type two and its causes, lifestyle, and complications. Additionally, there was one video focused on diabetes type one, however, it was about a single-person experience with diabetes type one and the video did not include information about the signs and symptoms or correct action.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

In conclusion, our study suggests that Saudi caregivers have a high recognition rate for diabetes presenting symptoms in children, and this could be related to the high incidence of type 2 diabetes in our community. However, they lack knowledge about the safest next course of action. We recommend tailoring our future national awareness campaigns to emphasize the importance of seeking urgent medical help once diabetes is suspected in a child. And it should be part of the information leaflet provided by Saudi MOH.

Variables	Can the participant recognize the common signs and symptoms of diabetes type 1?		P-value
	Yes N(%)	No N(%)	
Dose the participants recognize the symptoms of diabetes?	233(62)	144(38)	
Do you have Diabetic patient in your family?			
No	62(46.97)	70(53.03)	<.0001
Yes	171(69.80)	74(30.20)	
Have you received awareness about diabetes?			
No	64(44)	80(55)	<.0001
Yes	169(73)	64(27)	
Do you have a healthcare provider in your family like a nurse, dentist, doctor?			
No	136(54.62)	113(45.38)	<.0001
Yes	97(75.78)	31(24.22)	

Table 1.0: This table show the statistically significant demographics and variables that affect participant in recognizing the common signs and symptoms of diabetes type 1

Variables	Did the participant chose correct or incorrect first step?		P-value
	Incorrect	Correct	
Gender [n (%)] Male Female	70% 38%	30% 62%	<.0001
Monthly income <4000 sr 4000-20000 sr >21000 sr	39 19.80 115 58.38 43 21.83	47 26.11 113 62.78 20 11.11	0.0149
Number of children 1 2 3 4 5 or more	35 17.77 37 18.78 33 16.75 40 20.30 52 26.40	16 8.89 26 14.44 34 18.89 38 21.11 66 36.67	0.0408
What is the relation with the patient others	47 37.60	27 22.50	0.0101
First relative	78 62.40	93 77.50	
how did you get the information? internet campaign brochures doctor relative/friend other	13 13.98 10 10.75 4 4.30 54 58.06 9 9.68 3 3.23	23 25.56 5 5.56 10 11.11 31 34.44 19 21.11 2 2.22	0.0046

Table 2.0: This table show the statistically significant demographics and variables that affect participant in choosing the correct course of action if suspecting diabetes

Figure 2.0: ttest of age by choice of correct/incorrect action

Figure 2.0: ttest of age by recognizing diabetes early signs and symptoms

Figure 3.0: this graph shows the correlation between Number of children and the choice of correct action in case of suspecting diabetes which show the more children the parent has the better course of action

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